

Prophylactic chemical treatments for control of bacterial blight (BB)

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BB is an important rice disease in the Cuu Long Delta. Many rice cultivars, especially medium and late (local) varieties grown, are susceptible to BB and yield loss is substantial.

We studied the effect of prophylactic chemical treatments for BB control in the greenhouse.

Streptomycin sulfate, ammonium sulfate, and IBP were sprayed on 20-d-old rice seedlings of moderately resistant varieties TKM6 and Zenith, and susceptible variety TN1 planted in pots. N was applied at 150 kg/ha. There were six replications with five plants/replication.

Effect of prophylactic chemical treatments on bacterial leaf blight disease,^a Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam.

Treatment	TKM6		Zenith		TN1			
	Test 1		Test 2		Test 1		Test 2	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
Ammonium sulfate	2.64	29.35	3.37	37.38	3.92	41.29	6.97	77.47
Streptomycin sulfate	3.40	37.47	4.25	47.89	4.90	45.43	7.72	85.78
IBP	3.43	37.43	3.45	39.90	4.80	50.31	7.69	85.07
Water	3.52	39.07	4.85	53.93	5.60	62.22	7.32	81.23
Unsprayed check	3.19	37.78	3.90	43.36	4.91	54.61	7.80	86.57

^aa = disease scale (0–9), b = disease index (%).

Chemicals at 500 ppm concentration were sprayed 15 d after transplanting. Water-sprayed and unsprayed plants were maintained as control. The BB pathogen was inoculated 5 d after chemical application by clipping the leaves with scissors dipped in fresh bacterial suspension. Reaction was scored 10 d after inoculation using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

The experiment was repeated twice and the disease index of the experiments are presented in the table.

Water spray tended to increase disease intensity. Spraying with ammonium sulfate 5 d before inoculation decreased disease intensity significantly in moderately resistant and susceptible varieties and was superior to the other treatments. □

Bacterial leaf blight (BB) pathotype at Pantnagar

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* is one of the most serious diseases in the tarai belt of UP. Recent studies at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, showed there are 2 major BB pathotypes—I and II—in India. Isolates of pathotype I are characterized by resistant

Reaction^a of some differential varieties to BB pathotypes, Pantnagar, India.

Variety	Pathotype I	Pathotype II	Pantnagar
DV85	R	S	R
Cempo Selak	S	R	S
TKM6	R ^b	—	R
BJI	R	S	R
IET4141	R	MS-S	R

^aR = resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bBased on reaction at Coimbatore.

reaction on DV85. Isolates of pathotype II are characterized by resistant reaction on Cempo Selak. We sought to identify the prevalent BB pathotype in Pantnagar.

In 1982 and 1983 kharif, varieties with known BB resistance were artificially inoculated by clipping technique with

naturally occurring BB inoculum. Disease reaction was scored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice 14 d after inoculation. Disease reaction at Pantnagar was compared with that at other locations (see table). In Pantnagar, the BB pathotype appears to be pathotype I. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Fungicides to control green muscardine fungus, a disease of zigzag leafhopper in rearing cages

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Zigzag leafhopper (ZLH) *Recilia dorsalis* (Motschulsky) frequently becomes infected with green muscardine fungus

Metarrhizium anisopliae in rearing cages during the wet season. We evaluated fungicides for *M. anisopliae* control.

The fungus was cultured on YpSs Emerson agar. Spores were mixed with the fungicides in sterile water containing 0.05% detergent as an emulsifier. The suspension was vortexed and the spores were spread on YpSs agar culture medium in a petri dish. Fungicides

tested were benomyl, mancozeb, thiophanate-methyl, and mebenil at 0.5, 1.6, 0.7, and 0.75 kg ai/ha, respectively, based on the area of the petri dish. Percent germination of 300 conidia counted randomly on each plate was determined after 24 h incubation at 25°C.

Benomyl, mancozeb, and thiophanate methyl did not allow fungus germi-